

IMPORTANT APPROACH TO TEACHING THE NEWEST HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article describes the new interpretations of the teaching the newest history of Uzbekistan in education system, including some aspects of the consistent reforms being implemented in the teaching of the subject. It discusses the priority tasks set for historians and specialists in the new Uzbekistan in this regard, as well as the necessity and urgency of their implementation. The article provides information about the choice of our acquired independent path of development, the return to our history and national spiritual values to our people, the era of self-awareness, and the urgency of studying the era of the new Uzbekistan.

Keywords: the newest history, heritage, ancestors, scientists, the priority tasks, ancestors, courage, path of development, historical environment.

The main strategy of modern education should focus on the student's independent activity, the organization of self-learning environments and experimental and practical training, where students have a choice of actions and can use initiative as well as flexible training programs. The change in social reality has made changes in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The priority is the issue of improving the quality of education, which is associated not only with institutional and organizational changes, but also with the introduction of new teaching methods.

In today's era of globalization, the task of forming a sense of pride and honor in the minds of our people, especially young people, for the formation and

development of our country's rich history and national statehood, and educating them in the spirit of love for the homeland, is becoming even more urgent. Indeed, the history of the Uzbek people and their statehood goes back a long way. We should rightfully be proud of this, and we should pass on this rich, material and spiritual heritage to future generations in our own way. For this, it is important to approach the teaching of history with new interpretations.

This article is also based on the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” and the analysis of the priority task of further developing the study and promotion of the history of Uzbekistan established therein, and the Concept for the Development of History until 2030. The article was based on the principles of objectivity, consistency, chronological study of historical and social events and phenomena, reliance on sources and evidence, and their validity, adopted in all social and humanitarian sciences.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” dated January 28, 2022, sets the task of “Further development of the study and promotion of the history of Uzbekistan” as Goal 77, and it provides for the implementation of the Concept for the Development of History until 2030, which confirms the importance attached to the study of the history of our people and their statehood at the level of state policy. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, “Let us never forget one truth: we are a people who created a great history, a great state, and a great culture. We are a great people who never shy away from work, are not afraid of difficulties, value justice, and are determined. If we all act as one, united and in harmony, if we work honestly and with good intentions, we are capable of achieving any goals, in other words, creating a new page in history.” Of course,

great scholars, virtuous people, scholars, and military leaders have emerged from this ancient and sacred place. The foundations of many religious and secular sciences were created and refined on this land. The fact that magnificent historical monuments and structures built in the past have not lost their beauty and charm to this day indicates that settled agriculture, developed handicraft culture, architecture, and urban planning have been highly developed in our country since ancient times. The fact that the head of our state put forward important proposals on the theoretical and methodological foundations and principles of studying this historical heritage is an important program in solving some problems in studying our true history during the years of independence. In particular, the honest critical analysis of some mistakes and shortcomings made over many years in this regard was also an important event. Expressing his views on this issue, our President notes the following: "Unfortunately, in the past, archaeological research was not carried out sufficiently in studying the history of our country. Therefore, it is necessary to organize the activities of the Institutes of Archaeology and Art History of the Academy of Sciences, archaeological research in higher education institutions and museums together with foreign partners. In the Address of the Head of State to the Oliy Majlis, it is stated: "We should pay special attention to instilling in the minds of young people the invaluable heritage of our great scholars and writers, the invincible heritage of our saints, the courage of our invincible commanders and figures, and strengthening their sense of national pride and honor. To this end, it is necessary to establish the "History of Uzbekistan" TV channel within the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan and, together with our scientific community and creative intelligentsia, to thoroughly shape its programs. It was noted that it is necessary to conduct a complete inventory of historical exhibits stored in the museums of our country, to create a catalog of each museum. In this context, it is necessary to talk about teaching the latest history of Uzbekistan. That is, this period is a period of choosing the path of our independent development,

returning our history and national and spiritual values to our people, and realizing our identity. The integral continuation of this period is the period of new Uzbekistan, which has given a new meaning to our national development and has begun a new era of development. After all, in recent years, new reforms have been implemented in our country to further strengthen the independence of Uzbekistan, democratize society, build a legal and democratic state, further develop civil society, glorify human dignity, ensure harmony and equality of all nations living in our country, and achieve socio-economic development of the republic. In order to have objective information about the latest history of Uzbekistan, it is important to correctly determine the subject and object of the science. Because the current One of the important issues facing historians today is to cover the history of the Uzbek people and their statehood based on the subject of science and the object of its study, based on the principles of truthfulness and objectivity, relying on new theoretical and methodological principles.

Therefore, it is appropriate to divide the period of the most recent history of Uzbekistan into the following two important historical periods:

- The period of Uzbekistan's independence and further strengthening during the years of (1991-2016)
- The period of new Uzbekistan and its strategic development during the years of (from 2017 to the present).

The most recent history, like other social and humanitarian sciences, is an independent science. It has its own place and status among all sciences and is studied in close connection with social and humanitarian and some other sciences.

Firstly, by its nature, it teaches about the history of the years of independence, encourages people to draw the necessary conclusions about the events and incidents that occurred, encourages them to appreciate the place of our state and society in our recent history.

Secondly, the study of history relies on all the principles and methods inherent

in all social and humanitarian sciences. It is not without reason that mathematical methods are even used in its study. Because historical events and incidents are studied with strict accuracy, in a periodic sequence, on a chronological basis. When studying them, attention is also paid to the authenticity of historical documents and evidence, when, where, and in what historical environment and conditions they were created. The newest science of history of Uzbekistan studies the social, political, and economic processes of our recent past, the reasons for their development. It encourages people to learn from them for the future and draw the necessary conclusions. This is of great importance for the development of future generations. The system of ensuring the country's continued integration into the world community, conducting an open pragmatic policy based on close neighborliness and strategic cooperation, and ensuring peace and security has been further strengthened and improved. A new mechanism for dialogue with the people and attention to human interests has been introduced. Solving many problems that have been accumulated over many years, strengthening the personal responsibility of each leader, living with the people's concerns, introducing a new system of working with citizens' appeals, and radically reforming the issues of attention to the human factor are great historical achievements of the new Uzbekistan. In recent years, in the teaching of the new history subject, increased attention has been paid to the issues of further increasing the well-being of our people, transforming economic sectors and developing entrepreneurship, unconditionally ensuring human rights and interests, and determining priority areas of reforms aimed at forming an active civil society, based on the principle of "Exalting Human Dignity". At the same time, special attention has been paid to the preparation and implementation of a set of measures aimed at promoting the image of Uzbekistan on the world stage, the effective continuation of the dissemination of objective information about the progress of reforms in our country, the processes of democratic renewal of society, and improving the regulatory and legal framework

of foreign policy and foreign economic activity, as well as the contractual and legal foundations of international cooperation. The science of the latest history of Uzbekistan gradually studies these historical processes and conveys them to future generations.

In general, the systematic study of the newest history of Uzbekistan based on the principles of historicism and objectivity will be a worthy contribution to our efforts to objectively assess the glorious past and present of the Uzbek people, who have a huge historical and cultural heritage and have made a great contribution to the development of world civilization. This sets before historians the task of coordinating the work on creating a new generation of educational, educational and methodological literature and textbooks, and studying the latest history of Uzbekistan in conjunction with the history of the peoples of the world and the region. This, undoubtedly, will ensure the study of the latest history of Uzbekistan not only in harmony with the reforms and changes carried out during the years of independence, but will also serve to achieve our future strategic goals.

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